

Development of Students' Independent Thinking Skills

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Education is a process aimed at educating a person in the spirit of universal and national values, as well as comprehensively developing a person and bringing them to perfection.

Thinking is considered a specific product of this process. History and even accumulated experience give us many examples that every person thinks in their own way. Thinking is a product of human consciousness that is expressed in relation to the environment, phenomena in reality, objects and people. Every person has their own way of thinking, their usual way of thinking to evaluate something. And this situation is not only characteristic of a number of people, but is also characteristic of entire peoples, states, and all stages. In every circle of people, in every era, there have been people who think differently from others and look at existence with different eyes. Non-standard thinking forms the basis of almost all discoveries, scientific innovations, and creations. They have always been the reason for the birth of ideas that lead humanity to progress.

The main content and specific features of students' independent thinking process can be seen in the following: in the process of completing a task, the student is freed from the teacher's help and remains face to face with a problem that is difficult to overcome. While completing such a task, the student must test his strength, find solutions and bring it to the end, relying on his knowledge, skills, personal observation and thinking. Only if the given task does not correspond to the student's level of preparation, the teacher can intervene and provide direct assistance in completing the task. Therefore, the given tasks should take into account the student's level of preparation. In this case, the teacher takes measures to eliminate certain difficulties. When we look at the practical results of the mentioned works, we see that there are a number of problems in front of us.

Current problems in developing students' independent thinking skills:

- Insufficiency of the network of institutions providing services aimed at providing

education and bringing to perfection, low efficiency of such types of services;

- Insufficiency of qualified, experienced teachers;
- Insufficiency of effective teaching methods, techniques, forms and means;
- Lack of cooperation between parents, community activists and subject teachers at the required level;

The above are considered as pedagogical problems in developing students' independent thinking skills, and their solutions serve to improve the quality of the educational process. A person who has his own opinion, his own analysis, and his own thought serves progress. Identifying the initial thoughts that arise in the student, developing them and bringing them to the form of an idea, controlling and completing this process is related to the teacher's activity.

Thinking (tafakkur) is considered the highest form of human intellectual activity, intelligence, communication process and conscious behavior. Independent thinking is a tool for knowing the environment, social environment and reality, as well as the main condition for carrying out human activity intelligently, reasonably and effectively. In the process of independent thinking, thoughts, considerations, ideas, assumptions, goals arise in a person, and they are expressed in the form of concepts, judgments, and conclusions in the mind. Independent thinking is closely related to language and speech and manifests itself in them, and they continuously demand each other. It is for this reason that a person stands out fundamentally from other beings by his independent thinking (communication), speech and conscious behavior.

In his independent thinking activity, a person determines the correctness, accuracy, truth, fairness or adequate understanding of the things and events he reflects, feels, perceives, imagines and remembers. He determines how accurate the judgments, concepts, conclusions, assumptions (guesses) and decisions made in the process of knowing existence are. Through independent thinking, a person generalizes reality, reflects it directly and indirectly, and understands the internal, complex connections, relationships, properties, characteristics and mechanisms between objects and events. Therefore, a person has the opportunity to foresee the emergence, course, development and consequences of natural and social phenomena and events based on certain laws, regularities and rules. Nowadays, the importance of independent thinking in organizing a person's cognitive and practical activities intelligently, fairly and effectively is increasing. In particular, it is also important for the student to understand the compatibility of theory and practice. However, based on practical analysis, we can

present the problems of how important this situation is in the socio-humanitarian educational process.

Problems in developing students' independent thinking skills in the socio-humanitarian educational process:

- Insufficient interest of students in academic subjects;
 - Failure to convey the connection between past, present and future to students at the required level;
 - Lack of formation of students' independent views on events and phenomena, in general on the topic;
 - Insufficiency of measures to develop students' thoughts and creative abilities;
- In this process, the student's thinking skill is turned into a qualification.

Usually, thinking is divided into several types according to the degree of generalization of reality, the nature of the means of solving the problem, the novelty of the object for the subject, and the indicator of the person's activity. When independent thinking is considered as a mental activity, solving problems and tasks by a person is considered, their conditions, essence, structure, forms and the person's ability to understand are observed. Solving a problem, problem, task (solving, performing) is considered in connection with the person's needs, interests, desires, behavior, abilities, talents, and competence, accepting their requirements, making a certain decision, and searching for means form a solid basis for independent thinking. Human recognition by a human, that is, determining the mental state of an unfamiliar person, guessing, collecting the most necessary signs and characteristics is also a product of independent thinking. This complex multi-stage cognitive process requires a person to exert willpower, intellectual seriousness, conscious attitude, stable situation, and favorable conditions, as a result of which a certain decision is made and a certain conclusion is reached.

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